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**A Philosophical Approach to »the Game, the Leisure and the
Childhood« in the documentary »Tarja Branca« from Nietzsche.**

Abstract: These are some thoughts about a documentary called »Tarja Branca »White Stripe« and an analysis of the psychological, anthropological and economical aspects, within a philosophical perspective, of the possible pedagogy and perspective which teachers and professors should and could have in the classroom. I believe that this kind of approach would enrich the lives of those involved: teachers, professors, and students. The idea is to make education as freely as possible, ridden of obligations and duties taken out of desire.

Keywords: Philosophy, Childhood, Kids, Teaching, Teachers, Professors, Psychology, Pedagogy, Freedom, Duty, Obligations, Educational Psychology.

I

It is seen in the documentary »Tarja Branca«¹ that all our children, whether they are in the literal biological, or taken in the age or psychological sense, or whether they are in the imaginary, figurative sense, or with a jovial, curious, creative, pure personality, are slowly murdered by the economic system, which gradually tries to insert them as mere automated atomic objects and as cogs in an engine, which sustain a system which only a few actually enjoy «say, less than 5% of the global population».

¹ https://www.videocamp.com/en/campaigns/quarentena-believe-tarjabranca/player?special_id=60311

The overwhelming majority of young people and children are trained, or conditioned, domesticated «not to say, as in psychoanalysis, 'castrated'» to believe that working eight hours a day on average, and for many more than ten hours a day on average, and earning a salary of a maximum of 3,500 reais is really worth it. This is considering the fact that almost all this capital at the end of the month will very likely be exhausted with the most “trivial” needs, such as food, transport, health, education, IPTU «a Brazilian State tax», water, electricity, among the many other burdens which, *exempli gratia*, the Brazilian people pay, but receive little in return from the State.

The point, however, that the documentary raises is that at work or in business, in general, people feel frustrated, in most cases, they are melancholic, sad, depressed, and inappropriately euphoric in the face of rewards and they develop, by the false solution to so much frustration or denial of pulse or pleasure, vices and diseases; thus, the affections start to be medicated, while the cause of the problem is not solved. After all, what would be the origin of the problem of 'business', or 'work as a business'?

As the documentary's psychoanalyst explains, the etymological definition, which follows the philological definition, of the term 'business' «‘negócio’ in Portuguese, comes from two words, the word ‘negation’ from the Latin verb *‘negere’*, to negate, and from the nominative noun *‘negatio’*, negation» and ‘leisure’ «‘ócio’ in Portuguese from the nominative noun *ōtium*, which means leisure-time activities, which in general, although serious, generated pleasure». Thus, the Greeks and Romans dispensed with the work that involved production and commercial and monetary activities, and practised leisure not to do anything, but to dedicate themselves to the arts, such as dance, poetry, music, theater, martial arts, sports, politics, to war, oratory, to philosophies, activities which were considered honourable and dignified, unlike the others. Therefore, work as a business is certainly, in the capitalist view, a denial of everything that most people like to do. The fact is that people don't ‘play’, they don't feel pleasure with what they usually do and since childhood they are denied this, forced to become adults and deny their playful, curious and creative side. In this regard, the philosopher Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche has something to teach us.

II

In Nietzsche's philosophy, especially in one of his favourite works towards the end of his creative life, namely, "*Also Sprach Zarathustra: Ein Buch für Alle und Keinen*"² or "Thus Spoke Zarathustra: A Book for All and None" Nietzsche presents us with arguments from three possible stages of the existence of an individual or human being, namely: The camel, the lion, and the child.

The camel is, as we can perhaps imagine, a beast of burden that wanders through the desert or through great arid voids, supporting a lot of weight, infernal heat, with little water; the camel, in fact, desires the heavy, gets used to the heavy, does its duty and tolerates, obeys... What we can understand from this allegory is that when we are being raised by our parents «when we were little» or we are being taught by teachers, we are not given a choice as to whether or not we can learn what is presented to us, but we are obliged to endure the whatever, and 'must' endure and learn what we are required to learn. This also means the values, norms, rules, morality and every type of duty that we are required to follow and not just knowledge of language, arithmetic or practical knowledge. But then, the camel, which is a strong spirit, wanders through the desert and decides to free itself from all the weight.

A metamorphosis then occurs: the camel becomes a 'lion'. The lion considers himself the king of the desert, the lion is powerful and eager for freedom, but in his kingdom reigns an ancient being, a dragon. This is the dragon that, when questioned by the lion with the question 'Who are you?', answers him, 'I am the dragon You-Ought'. The word 'duty' is engraved on each scale of the dragon. The dragon brandishes 'Apart from me no one will create any new value, I am the ages of all values and duties, and there will be no more for anyone an 'I want'. The lion, of pure and courageous heart, roars the 'holy no!', and then fights the dragon to become free and king of the desert. If the lion is able to defeat the dragon, he begins to desire new thoughts and new values, and he begins to want to be the master of himself...

Thus, at last, the last metamorphosis of this intrepid spirit takes place; the lion becomes a 'child'. The child is a creator who plays, his act of creativity is play, curiosity and purity, because he left behind all the weight that was imposed on him, he got rid of

² This classic of philosophy was written by Nietzsche between 1883 and 1885.

the duties he didn't want to follow, and he became a master-of-himself, a wheel that propels itself... The child is a 'sacred yes!'. The child, as the Latin noun suggests «in Portuguese, the term is 'criança', the plural is 'crianças', from the verb "*creare*", to create», is a creator of new values, theories, laws, sons and daughters, or an instigator of creation; and finally, creates while playing.

It can be noted that these allegories do not imply referring to any image, concept, or phenomenon in particular regarding the exact age range, biological or psychological that these metamorphoses are indicated to occur. For Nietzsche, however, an individual only becomes an individual in the full sense of the term «I mean by that: fully unique and aware of it, a good or happy conscience», when he abandons the certainties that other individuals have taught him, lives his life, and re-value for themselves those values they would like to live by or creating the values «theories, arguments, ideas, practices, &c.» himself. I believe that it is precisely in this line of creative thinking, originality, play, and freedom that education should take place, and what educators should be, whoever they may be, in the lives of other individuals «and not just children, of course». Therefore, teachers and educators could create educational methods that, following this line, would, in my opinion, be very fruitful and much more palatable.